

What could be the result of $(1/0) + (1/0)$?

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Abstract

Indeterminate forms are still a problem in mathematics. However, as long as we are authorized to rely on certain mathematical rules, we may approach step by step even to cope with these mathematical issues.

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1. Introduction

An E-Mail reached me with the following content:

Practical illustration: The relationship between the focal length f of a lens, the object distance u and the image distance v is

$$1/f = 1/u + 1/v$$

Let there be only the lens- no object. If the object does not exist, no image exist and consequently u and v do not exist. So $u=0$ and $v=0$. The reciprocals of u and v do not exist when u and v do not exist. Thus

$$1/f = 1/0 + 1/0 = 0 + 0 = 0.$$

or

$$1/f = 0.$$

Multiply both sides by f^2 . We have

$$f = 0.$$

But we must not conclude from this that the focal length does not exist.

Because of the fundamental meaning of questions like these, I feel obliged to lose view words on this topic.

2. Material and methods

Definition 1. (The number + 1)

Let c denote the speed of light in vacuum (Drude, 1894; Tombe, 2015; W. E. Weber & Kohlrausch, 1856; W. Weber & Kohlrausch, 1857), let ε_0 denote the electric constant and let μ_0 the magnetic constant. Let i denote the imaginary number (Bombelli, 1579). The number +1 is defined as the expression

$$+(c^2 \times \varepsilon_0 \times \mu_0) \equiv +1 + 0 \equiv +1 - 0 \equiv -i^2 = +1 \quad (1)$$

while “=” denotes the equals sign (Recorde, 1557) or equality sign (Rolle, 1690) used to indicate equality and “-” (Pacioli, 1494; Widmann, 1489) denotes minus signs used to represent the operations of subtraction and the notions of negative as well and “+” denotes the plus (Recorde, 1557) signs used to represent the operations of addition and the notions of positive as well.

Definition 2. (The number + 0)

Let c denote the speed of light in vacuum (Drude, 1894; Tombe, 2015; W. E. Weber & Kohlrausch, 1856; W. Weber & Kohlrausch, 1857), let ε_0 denote the electric constant and let μ_0 the magnetic constant. Let i denote the imaginary number (Bombelli, 1579). The number +0 is defined as the expression

$$+(c^2 \times \varepsilon_0 \times \mu_0) - (c^2 \times \varepsilon_0 \times \mu_0) \equiv +1 - 1 \equiv -i^2 + i^2 = +0 \quad (2)$$

while “=” denotes the equals sign (Recorde, 1557) or equality sign (Rolle, 1690) used to indicate equality and “-” (Pacioli, 1494; Widmann, 1489) denotes minus signs used to represent the operations of subtraction and the notions of negative as well and “+” denotes the plus (Recorde, 1557) signs used to represent the operations of addition and the notions of positive as well.

Remark 1.

The definition of the basic numbers +1 and +0 in terms of physical “constants” provides the possibility to test **classical logic or mathematical theorems** et cetera by reproduceable physical experiments. In particular, it is very remarkable that Leibniz (Leibniz, 1703) himself published in 1703 the first self-consistent binary number system representing all numeric values while using typically 0 (zero) and 1 (one).

Definition 3. (Lens equation)

Let it be generally valid, that

$$\left(\frac{1}{a}\right) + \left(\frac{1}{b}\right) = \left(\frac{1}{c}\right) \quad (3)$$

3. Results

THEOREM 3.1

The general form of the equation

$$\left(\frac{1}{a}\right) + \left(\frac{1}{b}\right) = \left(\frac{1}{c}\right) \quad (4)$$

is the relationship

$$(a) + (b) = \left(\frac{a \times b}{c}\right) \quad (5)$$

Direct Proof.

It is **assumed** that the equation

$$\left(\frac{1}{a}\right) + \left(\frac{1}{b}\right) = \left(\frac{1}{c}\right) \quad (6)$$

is **generally valid**. Rearranging, we obtain

$$\left(\frac{b}{a \times b}\right) + \left(\frac{a}{b \times a}\right) = \left(\frac{1}{c}\right) \quad (7)$$

Rearranging further, it is

$$\left(\frac{b \times (a \times b)}{a \times b}\right) + \left(\frac{a \times (a \times b)}{b \times a}\right) = \left(\frac{a \times b}{c}\right) \quad (8)$$

Under conditions were

$$\left(\frac{(a \times b)}{(a \times b)}\right) = +1^2 = +1 \quad (9)$$

it is

$$(a) + (b) = \left(\frac{a \times b}{c}\right) \quad (10)$$

Quod erat demonstrandum.

THEOREM 3.2

Under conditions where $\mathbf{a = b = 0}$ we obtain

$$\left(\frac{(a \times b)}{a \times b}\right) = \left(\frac{(0 \times 0)}{0 \times 0}\right) = +1^2 \quad (11)$$

Direct Proof.

It is

$$\left(\frac{(a \times b)}{a \times b}\right) = +1^2 \quad (12)$$

Under conditions where $a = b = +0$, we obtain

$$\left(\frac{(a \times b)}{a \times b}\right) = \left(\frac{(0 \times 0)}{0 \times 0}\right) = +1^2 \quad (13)$$

Quod erat demonstrandum.

THEOREM 3.3

The value of $(1/c)$ under conditions where $a=b=0$ follows as

$$\left(\frac{1}{c}\right) = \left(\frac{2}{0}\right) \quad (14)$$

Direct Proof.

The equation

$$\left(\frac{1}{a}\right) + \left(\frac{1}{b}\right) = \left(\frac{1}{c}\right) \quad (15)$$

is accepted as **generally valid**, in other words even if $a=b=0$. However, under conditions were **$a=b=0$** , it follows that

$$\left(\frac{1}{0}\right) + \left(\frac{1}{0}\right) = \left(\frac{1}{c}\right) \quad (16)$$

while the value of $(1/0)$ and the value of $(1/c)$ may stay unknown. However, whatever the value of $(1/0)$ may be, the equation before demands equally that

$$1 \times \left(\frac{1}{0}\right) + 1 \times \left(\frac{1}{0}\right) = \left(\frac{1}{c}\right) \quad (17)$$

or that

$$(1 + 1) \times \left(\frac{1}{0}\right) = \left(\frac{1}{c}\right) \quad (18)$$

or that

$$(2) \times \left(\frac{1}{0}\right) = \left(\frac{1}{c}\right) \quad (19)$$

The general validity (including zero) of the equation

$$\left(\frac{1}{a}\right) + \left(\frac{1}{b}\right) = \left(\frac{1}{c}\right) \quad (20)$$

demand us to accept too that

$$\left(\frac{2}{0}\right) = \left(\frac{1}{c}\right) \quad (21)$$

Quod erat demonstrandum.

However, this theorem is still not an answer to the question, **what is the value of c in general?**

THEOREM 3.4

Under conditions where $((a+b)/(a+b)) = 1$, the value of c is

$$c = \left(\frac{a \times b}{((a) + (b))} \right) \quad (22)$$

Direct Proof.

As proofed by theorem 3.1, we have to accept that the equation

$$(a) + (b) = \left(\frac{a \times b}{c} \right) \quad (23)$$

is **generally valid**. Dividing by $(a+b)$, it is

$$\left(\frac{(a) + (b)}{(a) + (b)} \right) = \left(\frac{a \times b}{c \times ((a) + (b))} \right) \quad (24)$$

Under conditions where $((a+b)/(a+b)) = 1$, we obtain

$$1 = \left(\frac{a \times b}{c \times ((a) + (b))} \right) \quad (25)$$

In general, the value of c follows as

$$c = \left(\frac{a \times b}{((a) + (b))} \right) \quad (26)$$

Quod erat demonstrandum.

However, even this theorem is still not an answer to the question, **what is the value of c under conditions where $a=b=0$?**

THEOREM 3.5

The value of c under conditions where $((a+b)/(a+b)) = 1$ and where $a=b=0$ is

$$c = \left(\frac{0}{2}\right) \quad (27)$$

Direct Proof.

As proofed by theorem 3.4, we have to accept that

$$c = \left(\frac{a \times b}{((a) + (b))}\right) \quad (28)$$

Which is valid under conditions where $((a+b)/(a+b)) = 1$. However, these conditions do not exclude that $a = b = 0$. Under these additional conditions ($a = b = 0$), it is

$$c = \left(\frac{0 \times 0}{((0) + (0))}\right) \quad (29)$$

According to Barukčić (I. Barukčić, 2020), it is $(0+0) = (1+1) \times 0 = 2 \times 0 = 2_0$. We obtain

$$c = \left(\frac{0 \times 0}{2 \times 0}\right) \quad (30)$$

According Barukčić (I. Barukčić, 2018, 2019b, 2019a, 2020; J. P. Barukčić & Barukčić, 2016) it is $(0/0)=1$. We obtain

$$c = \left(\frac{0 \times 0}{2 \times 0}\right) = \left(\frac{0}{2}\right) \quad (31)$$

Quod erat demonstrandum.

THEOREM 3.6

Under conditions where $a = b = 0$, it is

$$\left(\frac{+2}{+0}\right) = \left(\frac{1}{\left(\frac{0}{2}\right)}\right) \quad (32)$$

Direct Proof.

In general, it is

$$+1 = +1 \quad (33)$$

is

$$+2 = +2 \quad (34)$$

Dividing by zero, it is

$$\left(\frac{+2}{+0}\right) = \left(\frac{+2}{+0}\right) \quad (35)$$

According to theorem 3.3, this equation changes to

$$\left(\frac{+2}{+0}\right) = \left(\frac{1}{c}\right) \quad (36)$$

However, theorem 3.5 demand us to accept that

$$\left(\frac{+2}{+0}\right) = \left(\frac{1}{\left(\frac{0}{2}\right)}\right) \quad (37)$$

Quod erat demonstrandum.

4. Discussion

In science, just as in real life, it is necessary to recognize and to overcome the difficulties resulting especially from the absence of defect-free thinking, behavior or work of one self and of others. One strategy can of course be simply to continue with very great personal effort to look the other way. However, anyone who cease to improve scientific knowledge and scientific methods and no longer wants to check the same or to make the same better, has stopped being a scientist.

Once and again, even view scientists prefer to fish in murky waters, a very systematic approach to an issue is of help and necessary too while stating clearly the foundations of own arguments. Otherwise, a scientist is opening himself up to suspicion that his primary goal is to keep alive an ongoing disinformation campaign or a campaign of false information while ignoring established facts. However, even under conditions of murky waters, logical contradictions are logical contradictions and the same can be identified as such while equally the same have to be avoided.

Nowadays and at former times, such attempt was doomed to failure.

5. Conclusion

Independent of the value of $(1/0)$ it is clear that $(1/0) + (1/0) = (2/0)$ as proofed by this pre-print.

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7. Author Contributions

The author confirms being the sole contributor of this work and has approved it for publication.

8. Conflict of Interest Statement

The author declares that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest. There are no conflict of interest exists according to the guidelines of the International Committee of Medical Journal Editors.

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